

GENDER RELATIONS IN WORKPLACE

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Abstract

This paper systematically reviewed current knowledge on workplace gender relations. It is believed that what might be applicable to one gender might be different from the other and this can affect the productivity of employees in an organization. The study adopted the exploratory research method. The study showed that there are still disparities in how men and women use power in organizations. These disparities, which are exacerbated by societal, organizational, and human variables, result in lost productivity since they restrict women's access to managerial opportunities and labor force participation. The study recommends that organizations should recognize the importance of diverse genders in organizations and to consider potentials and ability of individuals irrespective of their genders.

Keywords; Gender relations, gender identity, gender stereotypes, masculinity, femininity.

Introduction

The discussion of gender issues and development in the African context will focus on the social construction of gender norms through cultural differences in gender roles (Ojalammi 2011). As mentioned by Akanle (2011), gender norms assign distinct roles, duties, assignments, and benefits to both the female and male. He continued, saying that if such a thing happens, it becomes problematic. Primitive role assignments and dichotomized distribution that favor the person or persons concerned. Gender plays a significant role in understanding professional interactions, as is becoming more widely acknowledged. Bottorff, Oliffe, Robinson, and Carey (2011) posit that

relationships and interactions between couples, family members, and peers can have an impact on health behaviors and outcomes due to the influence of masculinities and femininities, as well as the interplay between and within them.

Shauri (2015) posits that while empowering women has been shown to have numerous benefits, it is crucial to understand that in certain societies, this empowerment may also increase family conflicts and domestic violence. Olonade, Oyibode, Idowu, George, Iwelumor, Ozoya, Egharevba and Adetunde (2021) opine that throughout the years, the prevailing trend has assumed male superiority while viewing women as feeble, inferior, and subservient; as a result, certain initiatives like the establishing the Family Economic Support Program and the Family Support Program Improvement Initiative and the Better Living for Rural Women Program and the formation of the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs in 1995. Each of these initiatives aimed to increase women's contribution to the advancement of societal goals for development. Unfortunately, this kind of women's development program has come under fire for neglecting to address and acknowledge the needs and welfare of real women. Instead of succeeding gender parity, implementing this strategy as a training initiative has exacerbated the issues and even made women's marginalization worse (Abdullahi, Adekeye, and Shehu 2011).

Oponng and Bannor (2022) in their examination of gender and power work relationships in Asia and Africa indicated that women's skill preferences, employment preferences, and disinterest in leadership roles are some of the factors contributing to some of the disparities they experience in the workforce. According to studies, women tend to develop skill sets that put them in low-paying occupations, for example, and avoid jobs where they anticipate having a harder time getting into the labor force or that put them at risk of repeated transfers (Gokulsing & Tandrayen-Ragoobur, (2014) in Oponng and Bannor (2022). Nevertheless, women in recent times now opt for same professions male genders opt for. The issue is what happens when they meet at the workplace even though they possess same skills and abilities that have been acquired through knowledge acquisition.

Statement of Problem

Gender today is no what it used to be in the past. In developed economies, women are given roles to play as a result of their perceived abilities. Generally today, there exists issues on gender relations in the workplace. In fact, equal

pay isn't the only aspect of gender disparity in the workplace. In addition to facing obstacles to assuming leadership roles, women—particularly black, LGBTQ+, and women of color—also frequently experience micro aggressions, which are hurtful remarks or insensitive inquiries pertaining to a person's race, ethnicity, gender, or sexual orientation (Woolf 2021). Shauri (2015) asserts that at the institutional level, women are frequently given unpaid tasks known as "women's work," which favors men over women and has a negative impact on both the health and financial security of women. Shauri (2015) further more draws attention to the existence of sexual division of labor at work place. He defines it as a social construct that assigns women to lower-paying, unequal roles in gender-specific occupations, while it also divides men and women into separate groups. Women are frequently given unpaid tasks known as "women's work" at the institutional level, which benefits men over women.

Cultural and moral African values are commonly instilled from home (Olonade, Oyibode, Idowu, George, Iwelumor, Ozoya, Egharevba and Adetunde 2021). These values are perceived to have a bearing on how individuals function in their workplace and relate with their peers. In a culture that sees female gender as the weaker gender, roles of leadership may not be given to females as every organization desires string leadership. It is hence assumed that as women rise in their career, in most cases it is assumed that their roles outside workplace are affected.

Research Objective

The objective of this study is to ascertain systematically gender relations in workplace.

Methodology

The research methodology is exploratory as it seeks to increase the understanding of the gender relation issues in work place.

Literature Review

Gender

Chiniara (2023) defined gender as an individual's self-identification as male, female, or non-binary; it can also be influenced by factors such as legal status, social interactions, public persona, personal experiences, and psychological context. She further opined that gender and sex have occasionally been used

interchangeably; this confusion is common. These terms are not interchangeable, though. Despite being connected to sex, gender is a distinct characteristic of a person. In the end, it comes down to how a person relates to how their culture perceives different gendered groups. A personal and internal perception of oneself as male, female, or other is referred to as gender identity. Gender is best defined as a dynamic structuring principle in society, according to Kuehnast and Robertson (2018). A person's biological sex (male or female) is only one aspect of it. What we do on an individual, social, and institutional level is ingrained with gender, which is a learned pattern of behavior. Gender mentality refers to how people—men, women, girls, boys, and members of sexual and gender minorities—are socialized and internalized to the roles and expectations that are deemed most desirable and appropriate by society. With the advent of new community beliefs, conventions, and expectations, a person's gender perspective might change. According to Shauri (2015), gender describes the material and conceptual connections that men and women have with one another, which are based on the beliefs, feelings, and actions that a certain culture associates with a person's biological sex. Rather than being defined by biology, gender is socially produced (Shauri 2015). Gender, according to Eklund, Barry, and Grunberg (2017), is a more nuanced and significant approach to comprehend individual differences. Particularly cultural norms influence how a person thinks about their gender and how other people perceive them (Shauri 2015).

Gender, in the words of Eckert and McConnell-Ginet (2013), is a pattern of interactions that emerges over time to identify male and female, as well as femininity and masculinity, while also organizing and governing people's relationships to society. Every facet of society is profoundly ingrained with it, including our institutions, public areas, artwork, attire, and modes of transportation. They went on to say that gender permeates every aspect of experience, from street games to government offices. It is ingrained in the media, the church, in school, the neighborhood, strolling down the street, dining out, and using the lavatory, and there is a connection between all of these contexts and circumstances in a structured fashion. A girl's desire for a frilly party dress and men's control over the means of production, as stated by Eckert and McConnell-Ginet (2013), are almost seamlessly connected since gender is so tightly organized at every level of experience. Within a broad gender order that both supports and is supported by these needs, what we perceive as our unique, possibly quirky, desires arise. This smooth transition between

language and gender is what gives language its significance. Even the tiniest of interactions can carry gender, and our continued behavior in those interactions reinforces gender's supporting function.

Gender Identity

A gender role is typically established by a culture or community and may have strict or ambiguous definitions based on how the community approaches establishing norms for any gender categories (Chiniara 2023). While gender roles are displayed in society by a set of expected behaviors or characteristics for a certain gender, gender identity is self-identified as it develops as a result of a combination of intrinsic and external influences. Additionally, the gender role (perceived "norms") for persons who identify as having a gender identity other than a binary male-female may not be expressed explicitly. Examples of such identities include gender fluid, agender, or non-binary identities.

Chiniara (2023), suggest that there are numerous possible combinations for gender identity, gender expression, and gender roles and these can vary throughout time. For instance, if a person identifies as male and prefers to speak of his own gender in terms of masculinity, then he or she has a male gender identity. He can be expected to dress a certain way or act in a certain way based on his gender role. In this case, his gender expression is masculine if he exhibits the stereotypically male traits of his culture in his actions, attire, and/or mannerisms. Regardless of his gender identity, if he deviates from those norms, his gender expression may be portraying a role that is not normally male. Gender identity, gender expression, and gender role are typically consistent across individuals (Chiniara 2023). It's critical to monitor a child's development in this area and identify incongruity, which can lead to gender-diverse behavior. Definitions must be stressed for clarity in order to comprehend gender identity development and related difficulties.

Gender Relations

Shauri (2015) defined gender relations as the social and economic ties that exist between men and women in any family, community, workplace, or setting. Gender relations affects people's capacity for freely choosing, influencing, exerting control over, upholding, and participating in group activities. Bottorff, Oliffe, Robinson, and Carey, (2011) opine that in several situations, gender relations emerged as a key discovery. Other researchers employed gender relations as a concept to analyze their findings. These studies have contributed

in a variety of ways to our understanding of gender relations. Gender relations did not follow a nuanced gendered perspective in certain investigations; instead, they were a broad inductively obtained conclusion that was neither integrated nor guided by the theoretical literature. In contrast, detailed explanations of the gender dynamics that arise from casual encounters were given in other studies.

Gender relations at the workplace

In organizations especially in developing economies, gender relations have an impact on the relationships between men and women; increases physical aggression and confrontation (Shauri 2015). This happens such that men are taught to be "masculine," and women are taught how to be "feminine". When men and women start to realize this and how it came to be widely practiced in their society, they will be able to change these learned attributes. The idea that women are less valuable and significant than men; the exclusion of women from certain roles (like leadership and decision-making); and the belief that women are to be subordinate to men. Women are perceived as backward, impoverished, illiterate, ignorant, and helpless, and are often blamed for problems. The true issue is gender relations, not women, as they influence women's access to power, education, and equal opportunities (Shauri 2015).

Ultius (2014) opines that in recent years, it's common to expect to have a balanced representation of both genders working side by side in the workplace, with no clear preference for having more male or female employees. However, it would still seem that gender roles play a significant influence in the day-to-day operations in some corporate environments after doing fieldwork in an office setting to observe the interactions between the male and female employees. An understanding of how an office established, maintained, and generally operated with the precise tasks that had been assigned to particular members during a business meeting was gained from the fieldwork conducted by Ultius (2014) through direct observation. The gender roles that the office workers were assigned based on their fieldwork reveal that the workplace is dominated by men and that female employees are expected to behave submissively and passively toward their male coworkers, who are viewed as authoritative figures by the other female employees. According to Ultius (2014), this is typical of traditional gender socialization and cultural contexts.

As stated by Wooll (2021), leaders must overcome the gender gap in career advancement and do away with discrimination in the workplace. This goal can be practically attained by open compensation, flexible work schedules, training opportunities for women, and an emphasis on mental and physical wellness.

This is because according to Ultius (2014), when it comes to distributing leadership and authority responsibilities across genders in the workplace, it is evident that traditional gender norms that have been ingrained in society have permeated and stayed true. Even though the image of the female is changing and being drastically reevaluated, it is evident that some parts of the business world, like the office that was seen during the fieldwork, have not yet recognized the new roles that women can and should be permitted to take. These elements make it clear that gender roles have been firmly related between male and female employees in the observed office (Ultius 2014).

Workers can help guarantee gender parity by forming alliances, denouncing discriminatory practices, and providing leaders with frank criticism (Wooll 2021). As opined by Ultius (2014), given that women have long fought for equality, gender plays a significant role in the workplace. A significant issue is the role of gender in traditional workplaces, while studies have indicated that women earn lower salaries than males. Other countries, such as Japan, have cultural traditions requiring women to serve tea to males. Nonetheless, progressive countries like the US have promoted more effective ways to achieve gender equality for women. An example of an explanatory sociology essay on gender roles in the workplace is provided below. It is from a "field work" study in which the behavior was noted and then documented (Ultius 2014).

In the findings from a conference room observations in Ultius (2014), the research's conclusions made it clear that there are clearly defined gender roles in this particular office—an instance of gender discrimination. It is clear from the conference room observations that men occupy the positions of authority and control in the workplace. Whenever a male presented a point or made an observation in a business conference, he would express his own arguments and be direct and concise in their approach, for example, saying, "we should do X." This is different from when a woman would raise an issue during a meeting since she would ask in a far more submissive manner, requesting consent from the other staff members with remarks like "I think point X is the best choice, isn't that right?" In general, the ladies communicated

in a way that was considerably more approval-speaking. The female staff members appeared to be assuming an expressive role in the workplace or making an effort to "cement relationships and provide emotional support and nurturing activities" (Lindsey). Relationships in the home frequently follow this pattern, and it seemed that the female staff members in this office were doing the same with their coworkers.

Gender stereotypes

Shauri (2015) defined gender stereotypes as oversimplified ideas about the characteristics, attitudes, or behavioural patterns of men or women. It serves as the foundation for sexism, which is the prejudice that values one sex over another." A Man's Place" and a "Woman's Place": Throughout history, there have existed two distinct worlds, one for men and the other for women, which are never to collide.

Ultius (2014) opine that it is clear that female employees in the organization play a considerably more subordinate role than male employees, giving the male employees more control and influence. It is clear that the long-standing gender stereotypes have seeped into and remained true when it comes to assigning leadership and authority roles in the workplace. Even if the perception of women is shifting and being critically reevaluated, it is clear that in some environments, such as the fieldwork workplace, there are particular locations in the corporate world that have. Gender stereotypes that normalize aggressive behavior, individuality, and taking risks, rewarding boys for these traits while rewarding girls for nurturing, compliance, and putting the needs of others before their own, make women invisible (Shauri 2015).

Masculinity versus Femininity

This relates to how roles are assigned to the sexes, which is another important problem in any culture for which there are many different approaches. A society is said to be masculine when there is a clear separation of emotional gender roles: women are expected to be more modest, sensitive, and life-quality-focused, while males are expected to be tough, forceful, and driven by material achievement. Conversely, a community is deemed feminine when emotional gender roles coincide, meaning that both sexes are expected to be modest, sensitive, and life-quality-focused (Hofstede, 2005 in Wu & Pan 2006).

Kuehnast and Robertson (2018) state that a socio-cultural approach

looks at how masculinity norms are impacted by violence and how men and boys then normalize using violence as a problem-solving strategy. The attitudes, ideals, and actions that society expects of boys and men are what define masculinity. Men make up the majority of combatants in war, and they also commit the majority of acts of violence during peacetime. Men are not naturally violent, though. This method recognizes the damaging long-term effects that violence and violent conflict—including sexual and gender-based violence—have on men and boys and the need to treat them.

The concept that males are inevitably violent people is replaced with the awareness that masculinities are social constructs that may be formed around peace by the peaceful masculinities approach. By working with young men through schools, summer youth camps, vocational training centers, and social media to promote nonviolent conceptions of manhood, including respect for people of diverse sexual orientation and gender identity, programs like the Young Men's Initiative in the Balkans seek to reshape social norms (Kuehnast & Robertson 2018). The concept that males are inevitably violent people is replaced with the awareness that masculinities are social constructs that may be formed around peace by the peaceful masculinities approach. The Young Men's I In an effort to separate violence from conceptions of manhood or masculinity, peaceful masculinities challenges men's acceptance of violence as a component of their masculinity. This strategy aims to highlight alternate, peaceful conceptions of what it means to be a man rather than to shame boys and men. This method would, for instance, inquire as to why boys and men do not turn to their friends and family for support when they are dealing with trauma.

Role Congruity Theory

Part of the inspiration for the Role Congruity Theory came from the social role theory, which holds that people form prescriptive and descriptive gender role expectations about the conduct of others based on the social positions that men and women occupy (Eagly, 1987; Samantha 2012). In the past, men have typically held higher status roles as breadwinners, which call for argentic traits like assertiveness, aggression, and independence, while women have typically held lower status roles as caregivers, which call for communal traits like empathy and other-orientation. Males are seen to be more argentic than women, whereas women are generally described as more communal than males. This sex-based division of social duties underlies society.

Because of this, female leaders are associated with transformational leadership styles, whereas men are associated with transactional leadership styles according to their temperament. By taking into account the congruency between gender roles and leadership positions and by putting forth moderators that affect congruity perceptions and the ensuing prejudiced behaviors, role congruity theory develops and broadens social role theory (Eagly and Karau, 2002 in Samantha 2012).

According to this idea, contextual moderators are likely to exist, giving rise to a female advantage in some circumstances and a male advantage in others, which will ultimately cancel each other out when the effects are summed up and combined. Furthermore, in situations when gender is not a significant factor for managers and staff or the duties at hand, there might not be any gender differences in measures of leadership effectiveness (Ridgeway, 2001 in Samantha 2012).

The theory of role congruity offers a thorough and useful explanation of bias towards female leaders. It suggests that bias against female leaders can differ based on a range of aspects of the leadership context and the traits of the people evaluating the leader (Eagly and Karau, 2002 in Samantha 2012). According to the theory, bias against women in leadership roles should be influenced by differences in how stereotypes are applied to specific women or how much a particular job is associated with men. These differences should have an impact on the frequency and degree of gender bias that arises.

Empirical Review

Primecz & Karjalainen carried out a study in 2019 on gender relations in the workplace: The experience of female managers in African harbours by presenting testimonies based on exploratory qualitative interviews with 26 female port managers from two North African countries and eight sub-Saharan countries. The findings showed that the interviewees in this sample are not subjugated women on the periphery of their societies. Rather, they are active agents who are capable of producing effective professional identities and mostly represent middle- or upper-class women in their societies. Although they face similar issues as those identified in previous women in management literature, including subtle or overt discrimination, work–life balance difficulties and a lack of recognition from male counterparts, their situation differs slightly from those in the West owing to their cultural, historical and religious context

2. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

3.1 Summary

The significance of gender diversity in the workplace and its effect on employees' productivity have been covered extensively in this study. Equal opportunities for men and women should be provided in organizations. According to the majority of research, different genders demonstrate various leadership philosophies. In fact, some research (Wu and Pan, 2006; Engen and Willemsen, 2001; Odumeru and Ogbonna, 2013) found that men were more transactional than women, who were more transformational than men. This finding demonstrated a substantial relationship between gender and leadership styles. Male leaders were strongly associated with transactional leadership styles and masculinity, whereas female leaders were closely associated with femininity, which was directly associated with transformational leadership styles.

3.2 Conclusion

Leaders need to eliminate workplace prejudice and close the gender gap in career advancement, according to Wooll (2021). Open remuneration, flexible work schedules, training opportunities for women, and a focus on mental and physical wellness are realistic ways to achieve this goal. This is due to Ultrius's (2014) assertion that it is clear that long-standing gender norms have permeated and remained true when it comes to the division of leadership and authority responsibilities among genders in the workplace.

3.3 Recommendations

The primary recommendation is for organizations to recognize the importance of both male and female genders in organizations and to consider potentials and ability of individuals irrespective of their genders. The existence of diverse gender should not be overlooked hence organizations, management and also employers are to target a strength so that it empowers the target rather than dehumanize them; this includes treating men and women equally and accepting them in an organization that promotes social justice and equity (Shauri 2015).

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